

MODERN TREATMENT AND MANAGEMENT OF NASOPHARYNGEAL ANGIOFIBROMA

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3rd year master's degree in otorhinolaryngology

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Annotation: This article deals with significant points about nasopharyngeal angiofibroma, its causes and symptoms. In addition to this, in the article modern methods of early detection and treatment of this disease were considered.

Key words: *blood vessels, Facial swelling, hereditary, precancerous polyps, Facial abnormalities, nasal cavity, radiation therapy, healthcare provider.*

Juvenile nasopharyngeal angiofibroma (JNA) is a type of harmless growth located at the back of your nose. These uncommon growths can grow quickly and cause a lot of harm to the structures around them, such as your sinuses, eye sockets, skull, and brain. Most JNAs happen to teenage boys and individuals who were classified as male when they were born. A juvenile nasopharyngeal angiofibroma (JNA) is a rare tumor that grows behind your nose. It is not cancerous. It mainly contains tubes that carry blood. Although these tumors are not cancer, they can still be dangerous and spread quickly. A JNA tumor can grow from your nose to your sinuses, eye area, skull, and brain. Another term for this condition is juvenile angiofibroma (JA).

The vast majority of JNA tumors grow in adolescent or prepubescent boys and people assigned male at birth (AMAB) between the ages of 10 and 20. Very rarely, it can appear in older men or boys as young as 7 years old. Nasopharyngeal angiofibromas almost never affect women or people assigned female at birth (AFAB). Nasopharyngeal angiofibroma is very rare. In the United States, there are only about 50 new cases each year. In the early stages, symptoms include:

- ✓ Frequent or severe nosebleeds.
- ✓ Nasal congestion.
- ✓ Runny nose.

Experts are not sure about the exact reasons behind JNA. Because these tumors mostly happen in people who were identified as males when they were born, it is probable that hormones have an effect on them. Experts do not think that JNA tumors can be passed down from parents to their children. There aren't many obvious risk factors for JNA. Even if it's not passed down through genes, you are more likely to get JNA if any of your biological family members have a rare disease called familial adenomatous polyposis (FAP). FAP causes precancerous polyps to grow in your large intestine. Experts continue to explore this relationship. Left untreated, nasopharyngeal angiofibroma can lead to:

- Difficulty breathing.
- Vision, hearing and speech issues.
- Facial abnormalities such as droopy eyelids or bulging eyes.
- Loss of sense of smell (anosmia).
- Severe nosebleeds and massive blood loss.
- Mental status change.

A healthcare provider can diagnose JNA during an examination. After looking at your nose, they'll ask about your symptoms. They may also refer you to an otolaryngologist (ENT) for further examination. If your healthcare provider

suspects JNA, they'll want to take imaging tests. These may include:

- I. CT (computed tomography) scans.
- II. MRI (magnetic resonance imaging).
- III. PET (positron emission tomography) scans.

They might also use a special tool called a nasal endoscope to see the tumor inside your nose. An endoscope is a long, bendy tube that has a light and camera on one end. A doctor will gently put a thin tube called an endoscope into your nostril to look inside your nose. They will use a spray that makes the area numb, so you may feel a little pressure, but you should not feel any pain. Surgery is the best way to treat a condition called juvenile nasopharyngeal angiofibroma in young people. Some people require radiation treatment as well. The treatment you receive for a JNA tumor depends on how big it is and where it is located. The purpose of surgery is to completely take out the entire JNA tumor. If the tumor is not too big or in a difficult spot, the doctor might be able to take it out of your nose using a small camera and special tools. A doctor who specializes in ear, nose, and throat surgery will do this procedure in a hospital. Sometimes, doctors can't take out the whole tumor because of where it is. If it's not possible to remove the tumor — or if it grows back after surgery — your healthcare provider may recommend repeat surgery or radiation therapy. This treatment uses high-energy X-ray beams to shrink the tumor. The outlook for people with juvenile nasopharyngeal angiofibroma depends on the size and location of the tumor. In most cases, a healthcare provider can remove the tumor or shrink it with radiation therapy. After treatment, your provider will schedule regular imaging tests to check for signs of recurrence (regrowth).

In up to 50% of cases, JNA tumors regrow after surgical removal. Regrowth usually occurs within two years after surgery, usually because a piece of the tumor still remains. If the tumor starts to grow again, your provider may schedule another surgery or recommend radiation treatments to shrink it. You should

schedule an appointment with your healthcare provider if you develop:

1. Frequent nosebleeds.
2. Difficulty breathing.
3. Persistent nasal congestion.
4. Runny nose.

To sum up all given facts above it should be noted that it is easier to prevent a disease than to cure it. In order to avoid this disease, it is permissible to strictly follow a healthy lifestyle. The longer you lead a healthy lifestyle during midlife, the less likely you are to develop certain diseases in later life. The more time a person doesn't smoke, eats healthy, exercises regularly, maintains healthy blood pressure, blood sugar and cholesterol levels and maintains a normal weight, the less likely they are to develop diseases such as cancer, hypertension, diabetes, chronic kidney disease and cardiovascular disease or to die during early adulthood.

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